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Experimental and numerical methods to assess the role of stReet trees as a Nature-Based Solution for climate change adaptation of Cities - Re.Nature Cities

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Re.Nature Cities

Experimental and numerical methods to assess the role of stReet trees as a Nature-Based Solution for climate change adaptation of Cities

WORK PACKAGE WP1 – Definition of the case study areas and simulation days

DELIVERABLE D1.1. – Case study areas and simulation days

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Table of contents

1.	Introduction	3
2.	State of the art.....	4
2.2.	Greek cities.....	9
2.3.	Simulation tools and methods	11
3.	Methodological procedure	16
3.1.	Selection criteria of the study area	17
3.2.	Case study LCZ areas	21
3.3.1.	LCZ2.....	24
3.3.2.	LCZ3.....	25
3.4.	Definition of simulation days	28
4.	References.....	47

1. Introduction

This deliverable presents the results of the identification process regarding the urban case study areas of the project for the city of Athens. The methodological procedure was based on the classes of the LCZ delineation (Agathangelidis, Cartalis, & Santamouris, 2020). The case study areas offer different morphological characteristics (buildings' geometry, land cover, building fraction etc.) so as to cover the majority of the typical metropolitan built environment of Athens.

Secondly, the selection of the simulation days (i.e., typical and extreme summer and winter days and typical spring days), for current and future climatic conditions, (i.e., projections for 2041-2060 and 2081-2100 and two emission scenarios) are presented.

- > **Task 1.1:** Collection of LCZ classification data for Athens and selection of the case study urban districts
- > **Task 1.2:** Definition of typical and extreme simulation days

2. State of the art

According to the UN, we are at a crucial moment in global urbanization, with over 50% of the world population already residing in cities, a number expected to rise to 70% by 2050, accommodating an additional 3 billion people (Joan Clos (UN-Habitat), 2015). Besides the unique opportunity for positive change through effective urban planning, rapid urbanization also poses risks, demanding a reevaluation of institutional frameworks to address challenges like climate change and disaster risks. More specifically, cities represent major contributors to greenhouse gas emissions, play a pivotal role in both contributing to and mitigating climate change. Hence, local authorities are increasingly taking the lead in terms of designing and implementing tailor-cut actions to tackle climate change, emphasizing the importance of low-carbon and resilient urban development. Following principles like compactness and inclusiveness unlocks opportunities for sustainable urban growth. In summary, strategic urban planning is vital for navigating the complexities and opportunities of urbanization, ensuring cities become hubs of prosperity, sustainability and resilience. Thus, urbanization will lead to approximately 6 billion urban dwellers by 2050, whilst cities will be exposed to the effects of climate change, such as high GHG emissions as well as intensified Urban Heat Island phenomena (McCarthy, Best, & Betts, 2010). More specifically, cities contribute approximately 70% of the world's carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions (International Energy Agency, 2021). With societies recovering from the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, there's a swift rebound in CO₂ rates, whilst the anticipated rise in global energy-related CO₂ in 2021 is poised to be the second-highest on record. Against this background, cities, serving as a significant global economic powerhouse, account for 80% of the global Gross Domestic Product (GDP), presenting a crucial opportunity to expedite efforts toward

ambitious climate objectives. Urban building stocks play an important role on the global share of energy consumption; in the developed countries they consume 20–40% of the total energy use, surpassing the consumption of transportation and industrial sector (Pérez-Lombard, Ortiz, & Pout, 2008).

Within this framework, the European Green Deal represents Europe's pathway towards a green transition, through a package of policy initiatives, with the ultimate goal of reaching climate neutrality by 2050. Fit for 55 represents the updated and concrete framework, regarding its targets of reducing net greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% by 2030. More specifically, Fit for 55 represents a set of proposals to revise and update EU legislation aiming at providing a consistent framework for reaching the EU's climate objectives, such as (i) just and socially fair transition to carbon-free economies, (ii) maintenance and strengthening of innovation and competitiveness of EU industry, (iii) ensuring EU's position as leader in the global fight against climate change (Council of the European Union, 2023).

In addition, the recast of the European Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) aims to align the rules for the energy performance of buildings with the European Green Deal and decarbonize the EU's building stock by 2050 (Article 14). District and large-scale policy measures are strongly encouraged as well (Article 8), whilst tackling energy poverty and protecting vulnerable consumers represent key aspects of the recast (Articles 21 and 22). The revision of EPBD translates the Commission's Renovation Wave Strategy into a concrete legislative action, which represents a dedicated regulatory framework and set of funding instruments to promote energy efficiency, building renovation and renewables deployment at building, neighbourhood and district level. Moreover, the new Energy Efficiency Directive (EED) introduces local heating and cooling plans for municipalities with a share of renewable energy reaching 100% by 2040, urging them to design related plans. Finally, the recast Renewable Energy Directive (RED) sets binding and indicative targets for renewables for buildings and district H&C systems.

Besides mitigation and adaptation of Climate Change techniques, tackling energy poverty and worst-performing buildings, represent important targets of the EU as part of the Renovation Wave strategy (nearly 34 million Europeans are energy poor) (European Commission, 2023). Renovation benefits have a dual positive impact, addressing the health and well-being of vulnerable people while reducing their energy consumption and bills. The Renovation Wave recognizes the need for promoting integrated, participatory and neighborhood-based approaches at the heart of its goals along with the uptake of investments into digital and innovative technologies. In addition, globally, 12,000 cities have submitted mitigation and adaptation Strategic Plans including building renovation strategies and energy poverty action plans, within the framework of the European Covenant of Mayors (CoM) initiative. Hence, CoM Action Plans could feed into the future updates of Long-Term Renovation Strategies and result in aggregated green procurement to which mayors commit under the Covenant. Finally, to further support long-term growth after the pandemic, the Commission's recovery plan further supports building renovations, since, given the labour-intensive nature of the construction sector, renovations will play a crucial role in European economic recovery after the COVID-19 pandemic. Moreover, the EU has introduced a just transition mechanism to provide financial and technical support to the regions most affected by the move towards a low-carbon economy, mobilising billions of funds dedicated to the facilitation of employment opportunities and reskilling, improving energy-efficient housing and fighting energy poverty (i.e. Greece).

2.1. Cities and UHI

Based on the international data, it is evident that measures must be taken in cities in order to tackle UHI phenomena, that affect urban health and adaptation parameters in cities. Hence, distinct air temperature variations emerge between urban zones and the surrounding rural landscapes, leading to the phenomenon known as the Urban Heat Island (UHI) (Oke, 1987). The UHI is intensified, among other factors, by the gradual replacement of permeable natural surfaces with coarse mineral materials like asphalt and concrete. This shift results in increased retention and re-radiation of solar radiation within the urban environment. Additionally, the reduced sky view factor contributes to trapping short and long-wave radiation within urban canyons, impeding natural cooling processes (Memon, Leung,

& Chunho, A review on the generation, determination and mitigation of Urban Heat Island, 2008). It's important to note that the UHI is not a static occurrence; its intensity (UHII) is higher on cloudless and windless nights and varies throughout seasons and daily cycles (Klisyik & Fortuniak, 1999; Kim & Baik, Maximum urban heat island intensity in Seoul, 2002; Kim & Baik, Spatial and temporal structure of the urban heat island in Seoul, 2005).

According to the 2023 World Population Data, mean projected changes in annual death rates per 100,000 people in countries that resulted from the impact of climate change on daily temperature, are constantly rising; For Greece the data refer to the annual average change for the period 2040-2059 under the Moderate Emissions scenario from the analysis presented by the Climate Impact Lab and UNDP and indicate an annual death rate of 10 per 100,000 people (Population Reference Bureau, 2023).

Picture 2.1 Rise in annual death rates per 100,000 people (Population Reference Bureau, 2023)

Cities face the critical need for efficient and holistic measures to mitigate UHI so as to improve thermal comfort conditions and reduce their building stock's carbon footprint due to increased cooling loads. More specifically, numerous studies have assessed the positive influence of UHI related measures in

urban Mediterranean areas (Oliveira, Andrade, & Vaz, 2011; Zinzi, 2016; Fintikakis, et al., 2011; Salata, et al., 2017; Santamouris, et al., 2012; Salvati, Coch Roura, & Cecere, 2017).

In Greece, the research focuses mainly in the cities of Athens (capital city) and Thessaloniki (second largest city), dealing with the influence of retrofitting of open public spaces (Chatzidimitriou, Chrissomallidou, & Yannas, Ground surface materials and microclimates in urban open spaces, 2006; Chatzidimitriou & Yannas, Microclimate development in open urban spaces: The influence of form and materials, 2015) and increased vegetation practices such as the implementation of green roofs in a larger scale (Karteris, Theodoridou, Mallinis, Tsiros, & Karteris, 2016). Based on a study regarding the five largest Greek cities, evaluated the UHI intensities, a surface UHI intensity of 3.3 °C in Athens and 2.7 °C in Thessaloniki, between rural and urban areas is evident (Stathopoulou & Cartalis, Daytime urban heat islands from Landsat ETM+ and Corine land cover data: An application to major cities in Greece, 2007). More recently, another study assessed the intensity of the Urban Heat Island in Thessaloniki and showing a variation between 2-3 °C during hot summer days (Giannaros & Melas, 2012).

UHI in Greek cities is linked not only to outdoor thermal comfort conditions, but also to increased cooling loads of the built environment (Hassid, et al., 2000; Santamouris, et al., 2001) as well as to smog release (Taha, 1994). Numerous studies analyzed the UHI phenomena in the city of Thessaloniki and other Greek cities (Balafoutis & Makrogiannis, 1998), (Stathopoulou & Cartalis, Daytime urban heat islands from Landsat ETM+ and Corine land cover data: An application to major cities in Greece, 2007), (Stathopoulou & Cartalis, Use of Satellite Remote Sensing in Support of Urban Heat Island Studies, 2011), (Stathopoulou, Mihalakakou, Santamouris, & Bagiorgas, 2008), (Stathopoulou, et al., 2010), (Papanastasiou & Kittas, 2011), (Dimoudi, Kantzioura, Zoras, Pallas, & Kosmopoulos, 2013), (Kolokotsa, Psomas, & Karapidakis, 2009), (Vardoulakis, Karamanis, Fotiadi, & Mihalakakou, 2013). Further studies analysed the improvement of the urban climatic conditions at district scale (Tsoka, Investigating the relationship between urban spaces morphology and local microclimate: a study for Thessaloniki, 2017; Tsoka, Tsikaloudaki, & Theodosiou, Urban space's morphology and microclimatic analysis: A study for a typical urban district in the Mediterranean city of Thessaloniki, Greece, 2017)

in the city of Thessaloniki, considering the unique typological features of the Greek built environments. In Thessaloniki IHU's maximum intensity ranges from 2°C to 4°C and 1°C to 3°C during the summer and winter periods (Giannaros T. M., Melas, Daglis, Keramitsoglou, & Kourtidis, 2013). Another study showed how urbanisation, lead to the intensity of UHI by approximately +0.2 °C per decade, since 1975 (Founda, Papadopoulos, Petrakis, Giannakopoulos, & Good) in the city of Athens, along with a seasonal change in the rate of UHI, accounting for approx. 40% of the observed warming rates of summer air temperature.

2.2. Greek cities

Greek cities have witnessed substantial growth since World War II, though governed by a centralized urban-planning system, that led to extensive and continuous built systems, characterized by social practices diverging from established scientific and technical planning norms (Papamanolis, 2015). Thus, the organization of Greek urban spaces, mainly Athens and Thessaloniki, has been and still is non-functional, featuring high building density, lack of coordination in central operations, restricted access to the natural surroundings as well as urban sprawl towards the city outskirts (Maloutas, 2000).

It is characteristic that Greek cities represent some of the most concentrated urban built environments in Europe, with 61.2% of Greece's total population residing in cities. The metropolitan areas of Athens and Thessaloniki alone account for over one-third (35.9%) of the entire population according to the Hellenic Statistical Authority. About 80% of the urban population inhabits the 18 largest cities, each exceeding 50,000 inhabitants, while the remaining 20% resides in another 66 cities with populations ranging from 10,000 to 50,000 inhabitants (Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2012). The compactness and density of Greek cities is undoubtable, whilst there is a strong relationship between Greek urban built environments and the energy efficiency of their building stocks (Tsirigoti & Bikas, 2017). Hence, according to Theodoridou et. al, 73% of the total population living in urban areas, mainly in the two largest Prefectures of Athens and Thessaloniki (Theodoridou, Papadopoulos, & Hegger, A feasibility evaluation tool for sustainable cities – A case study for Greece, 2012). More specifically the population density in the Municipality of Athens rises up to 19,133.41 people/km² with an even higher

concentration in Thessaloniki, reaching 20,429.20 people/km², compared to Berlin (3,796.30 people/km²), inner London (8,902.00 people/km²), Stockholm (280.90 people/km²), and Zurich (733.50 people/km²). Hence, Greek cities diverge in their typological features, concerning built-up density compared to Western-European and North-American cities, as post-war Greek urban architecture lacks a distinct 'own identity', leading to its manifestation in disorderly forms (Gospodini & Beriatos, 2006).

Thus, Greek cities have less green space per person compared to other European cities; according to data from the European Environment Agency, regarding the percentage of total green infrastructure, urban green space and urban tree cover in the area of EEA-38 capital cities, Athens is in the second last position, before Valletta. Hence, Athens features 11% urban tree cover and 17% total green infrastructure, while the related numbers for EEA-38 cities average are 30% and 42% respectively (Figure 2.1) (European Environment Agency, 2022).

Figure 2.1 Percentage of total green infrastructure, urban green space, and urban tree cover in the area of EEA-38 capital cities (European Environment Agency, 2022)

The above data underline the lack of accessible green spaces in Greek cities, as a significant portion of the city surfaces is covered by asphalt roads and concrete pavements (Papamanolis, 2015). More specifically, the defining feature of Greek cities is residential buildings, particularly the prevalent MF-building typology known as Polykatoikia (Greek: polys—many and katoikia—dwelling). Despite diverse influences from Italic, German, Ottoman, and French rule, as well as remnants of ancient Greece and Byzantium, Polykatoikies persist as a dominant architectural form across all Greek urban areas, regardless of climatic conditions or historical contexts. In both Thessaloniki and Athens, roughly 80% of buildings serve purely residential purposes, with 90% of mixed-use located in Polykatoikies, predominantly featuring apartments (Theodoridou, Papadopoulos, & Hegger, Statistical analysis of the Greek residential building stock, 2011). It is evident that the typology of Polykatoikia serves as the central and pervasive element in Greek cities; measures to reduce IHU and improve the built environment of Greek urban centers will have a direct positive impact on their domestic building stock, with various benefits in terms of social aspects besides reduced residential energy consumption. This was shown in a research concerning the influence of large-scale green roof implementation in Thessaloniki; the results showed that the implementation of GR in the residential building stock can lead reduced heating and cooling consumptions up to 5% and 16% respectively (Theodoridou, Karteris, Mallinis, Tsiros, & Karteris, 2017). Hence, methods to increase grass coverage and greenspace overall is considered to be an important tool, towards IHU minimization and urban cooling in Greek cities (Tseliou, et al., 2022), (Georgi & Dimitriou, 2010), (Dandou, Papangelis, Kontos, Santamouris, & Tombrou, 2021).

2.3. Simulation tools and methods

Simulation tools for the microclimate

Over the past years, several tools have been developed and use so as to assess the non-linear complex world of outdoor environment, call are the celebrated micro-climate numerical simulation tools. There

are various numerical models for different length scales (e.g. urban canyon, urban block etc.), as well as different degrees of complexity depending on the objectives of the respective study. Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations prove effective in evaluating thermal interactions at the micro-climate scale, providing high spatial resolution. However, they face limitations in large-scale case studies due to their significant computational cost. Some commonly used micro-climate tools include ENVI-met, SOLENE-microclimat (Musy, Malys, Morille, & Inard, 2008) and UrbanMicroclimate (Urban Microclimate, n.d.). (Musy, Malys, Morille, & Inard, 2008) and UrbanMicroclimate (Urban Microclimate, n.d.).

For this project the simulation tool ENVI-met is going to be used, a three-dimensional (3D) simulation tool, which can model the surface-plant-air interactions of the micro-scale urban environment. Utilizing thermodynamics and Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD), ENVI-met employs the standard $k - \epsilon$ turbulence model, including the equations of Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS). The program has a fine-resolution cell grid ranging from 0.5 to 10m, allowing it to simulate processes such as vapor and heat exchange at ground or wall levels, flows around and between buildings, exchange of mass and energy between plants and their environment, and particle dispersion. In terms of thermal comfort, the tool can assess the Predicted Mean Vote (PMV/PPD), and the Physiological Equivalent Temperature (PET), Universal Thermal Climate Index (UTCI), as well as the Standard Effective Temperature (SET). ENVI-met also encompasses detailed building physics, including façade temperatures, energy fluxes and solar access analysis, whilst the input data for the model involves meteorological data and the configuration/materials of the area (Figure 2.2).

The tool has been validated with field experimental measurements by several researchers; Chow et al. (Chow, Pope, Martin, & Brazel, 2011) managed to compare air temperature data from a bicycle traverse across a hot and arid city with the simulated outputs of ENVI-met V3. Krüger et al. (Krüger, Minella, & Rasia, 2011) found that ENVI-met overestimates wind velocities if the input wind velocity is over 2m/s at the height of 2.1 m above ground level. Chow and Brazel (Chow & Brazel, Assessing xeriscaping as a sustainable heat island mitigation approach for a desert city, 2012) validated ENVI-

met with observed data in a desert city and found that the tendency of the simulated daytime temperatures is to be lower than the measured ones. Several more studies also agree that the model tends to underestimate diurnal ambient temperatures (Chow, Pope, Martin, & Brazel, 2011; Emmanuel & Fernando, 2007). Ng et al. (Ng, Chen, Wang, & Yuan, 2012) verified ENVI-met outputs with both long-term data acquired from a meteorological station and in situ spatially distributed measurements in a typical dense urban area in Hong Kong.

Figure 2.2 Data flow overview of the simulation tool ENVI-met (Ampatzidis, 2018).

All the previous studies verified that ENVI-met, and particularly ENVI-met's version 3.0 or 3.1, can simulate with reasonable degree of correctness the outdoor air temperature, relative humidity and wind velocity for different climates (hot, dry, desert, humid). Despite their acknowledged academic value, these studies failed to deal with more inclusive variables. ENVI-met V4 includes for the first time the possibility of forcing the model (*“full forcing”*) with user-modified weather data in order to approach the dynamic behavior of the micro-climate. Yang et al. (Yang, Zhao, Bruse, & Meng, Evaluation of microclimate model for predicting the thermal behavior of different ground surfaces,

2013) worked with the new ENVI-met V4 (4.0) and managed to validate its simulated thermal characteristics (soil temperature, soil heat fluxes at surface etc.) of several ground surfaces (tile, asphalt, concrete and grass) during a hot/warm summer period. Acero and Herranz-Pascual (Acero & Herranz-Pascual, 2015) compared ENVI-met outputs with meteorological measurements from four urban areas with different micro-climatic conditions during typical summer days in Bilbao, Spain. There are numerous more studies that used ENVI-met for validation purposes but also to assess the influence of urban bioclimatic renovation measures in cities and predict the reduction of IHU related air-temperatures especially during summer periods, through large-scale implementation of vegetation, water sources and specific materials.

Simulation tools for buildings

Among the various tools for building energy simulation (BES), dynamic simulation programs are favored for their advanced numerical models capable of handling the time-related complexities of buildings and user behavior. The work of Crawley et al. (Crawley, Hand, Kummert, & Griffith, 2008) is one of the most comprehensive related papers, providing a comparative analysis of twenty BES tools in fourteen major categories, such as general modelling features, building envelope and daylighting. The study delivers valuable information on how each tool performs in each category. One of the most popular whole building simulation programs, which will also be used in this project, is EnergyPlus, a free console-based program, with open source code, that was developed by the U.S. Department of Energy (DOE) based on two older tools, BLAST and DOE-2.1E (EnergyPlus, n.d.; Crawley D. , et al., 2001). Apart from being the most globally established building simulation program, EnergyPlus is the base over which several programs have been developed, such as DesignBuilder (DesignBuilder, n.d.) and OpenStudio (OpenStudio, n.d.). Other BES tools are TRNSYS (TRNSYS (Transient System Simulation Tool), n.d.), eQUEST (eQUEST, n.d.), IDA-ICE (IDA ICE, n.d.) and ESP-r (ESP-r, n.d.). It is important to highlight the fact that several academic studies (Bozonnet, Belarbi, & Allard, 2007; Cóstola, Blocken, & Hensen, 2009) showed that BES programs fail to capture the dynamically changing outdoor micro-climate, which indeed affects building energy performance.

Coupling methods

Numerical tools have continuously evolved over the past decades to meet the needs of precise and fast retrofitting assessments in both building unit well and city scales. More specifically, Building Energy Simulation (BES) tools are capable of simulating the energy performance of a building unit, by incorporating heat flows through the building's envelope, solar and interior heat gains, occupancy patterns, detailed analysis of the performance of HVAC systems, daylighting, thermal comfort, wind movement and more. However, these tools, although working with climatic data, cannot compute dynamically the direct influence of outdoor micro-climate conditions and fluxes and, therefore, can only provide an approximation of the building performance. In most cases, BES programs are fed with meteorological data from nearby stations, created from statistical analyses derived from long-term observations. Hence, these data are not representative of the fluctuations in micro-climatic conditions that affect the building, such as the Urban Heat Island effect, vegetation etc.

On the contrary, the microclimatic conditions can be effectively modeled using various micro-climate simulation tools. These tools enable the calculation of surface and air temperatures, relative humidity, wind speed, mean radiant temperature (MRT). The outcomes primarily rely on provided weather data, soil type, temperature profiles, urban configuration (structures, distances, building height) and the physical properties of building materials and existing vegetation.

It is evident that there isn't a single tool specifically designed to directly assess the impact of micro-climate on a building's energy performance. In the last 15 years, researchers have been integrating building energy models with urban canopy models. These models come in either single-layered (Bueno, Norford, Pigeon, & Britter, A resistance-capacitance network model for the analysis of the interaction between the energy performance of buildings and the urban climate, 2012; Martin, Afshari, Armstrong, & Norford, 2015; Bueno, Norford, Pigeon, & Britter, Combining a Detailed Building Energy Model with a Physically-Based Urban Canopy Model, 2011; Ryu, Baik, & Lee, 2011) or multi-layered forms (Salamanca, Krpo, Martilli, & Clappier, 2010; Kikegawa, Genchi, Yoshikado, & Kondo, 2003;

Kikegawa, Tanaka, Ohashi, Ihara, & Shigeta, 2014; Kondo, et al., 2005). However, this approach may offer low spatial resolution as the boundary conditions are presented in two dimensions.

An approach increasingly adopted by several studies in recent years to achieve a three-dimensional representation of boundary conditions involves the development of a suitable coupling methodology between Building Energy Simulation (BES) and Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) micro-climate simulation tools. This approach aims to provide reasonable simulation times while preserving the model's capabilities. The initial studies on the theoretical development of coupling methodologies focused primarily on the interior environment of a building (Zhai, Chen, Haves, & Klems, 2002; Zhai & Chen, Solution characters of iterative coupling between energy simulation and CFD programs, 2003; Zhai & Chen, Performance of coupled building energy and CFD simulations, 2005). Subsequent studies developed full dynamic coupling procedures, although some simplified infrared exchanges and wind processes (Bozonnet, Belarbi, & Allard, 2007) while others did not consider the entire building climatic environment (Cóstola, Blocken, & Hensen, 2009). Bouyer et al. (Bouyer, Inard, & Musy, 2011) developed a simulation platform for coupling microclimate and building simulation tools to investigate the impact of various urban designs on a building's energy demand and found that solar irradiance predominantly influences building consumption.

3. Methodological procedure

In this chapter, the methodological procedure concerning the areas chosen is analyzed. Although the urban built environment of Greek cities is mainly characterized by density and MF-buildings, it was important to determine specific parameters of various sub-typologies within Athens's urban canopy.

Against this background, important aspects affecting the microclimate of urban areas would be:

- a) The density of buildings and the built-up system
- b) The height of the buildings
- c) The width of the streets
- d) Other parameters such as
 - The ability to expand the pedestrian zone for planting

- Socioeconomic aspects (i.e. characteristics of blighted areas)
- Typical and repetitive -in terms of its typology- area

The following diagram depicts the flow path of the decision-making process in order to choose the most representative areas (Figure 3.1).

Figure 3.1 Methodological flow-chart used for choosing the study areas

In the following chapters, the details of the project will be described, namely:

- > STEP1 – including the categorization of urban built spaces in Athens based on various typological features,
- > STEP2 – adding extra parameters to ensure the efficiency of the project,
- > STEP3 – final areas selection

3.1. Selection criteria of the study area

A thorough study by Agathangelidis et al. (Agathangelidis, Cartalis, & Santamouris, 2020), analyzed the relationship between various urban surface parameters and land surface temperature (LST) in 25 European cities, focusing on impervious fraction (imp), building density (b), and building height (H), parameters that also describe the urban built morphology of cities. The analysis used dedicated

statistical techniques and modeling approaches to assess how these parameters influence LST during daytime and nighttime. The most important key findings are:

Impervious Fraction (imp):

- Impervious fraction consistently showed a positive influence on LST across most cities.
- The positive correlation is attributed to decreased evapotranspiration in more heavily developed areas, leading to higher temperatures.

Building Density (b) and Building Height (H):

- During daytime, the relationship between building density (b) and building height (H) with LST varied across cities.
- After adjusting for imp, b, and H showed either weak positive or negative influences on LST during the day. High-rise buildings contributed to a slight decrease in daytime surface temperature in many cases.
- At nighttime, b and H exhibited a more consistent positive influence on LST, often with similar magnitudes to imp.

Spatial Regression Models:

- Spatial regression models supported the conclusions from multiple regression models, indicating the overall consistency of the findings.

Urban Area of Athens Analysis:

- The study conducted a focused analysis on Athens, considering the Local Climate Zone (LCZ) scheme and additional surface parameters.

- In the urban core of Athens, a negative relationship of LST with building height-to-width ratio (H/W) and compactness (c) was observed during the daytime, while a positive association was noted at nighttime.
- WRF numerical simulation for Athens showed that the model could reproduce main spatial patterns of the urban area, with some systematic underestimations, especially for heavily vegetated areas.

Overall, the study emphasizes the importance of considering diurnal variations in surface temperature when assessing the urban heat island effect, while building density and height showed a complex relationship with LST, the study highlights that the impact varies based on local conditions, ventilation potential, and other factors. In addition, the Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) model, coupled with the Single-Layer Urban Canopy Model (SLUCM), provided reasonable estimations of surface temperature and near-surface air temperature. Moreover, systematic errors were identified, such as nighttime temperature underestimations in well-vegetated areas, possibly influenced by the location of meteorological stations and the modeling approach. Hence, the findings contribute to a better understanding of the urban surface parameters influencing LST, which is crucial for climate-sensitive urban planning and mitigation strategies, underscoring the need for accurate modeling approaches that consider the complexities of urban environments, including vegetation and building interactions.

Based on all the above, the LCZ categorization for Athens proposed by Agathangelidis et al. was considered as a solid base for the parametric analysis and choice of the study areas for this project (Agathangelidis, Cartalis, & Santamouris, 2020). More specifically, for the case of Athens, the study highlighted unique characteristics influencing land surface temperature (LST). The negative daytime relationship between LST and building height-to-width ratio (H/W) and compactness (c) in the urban core underscores the mitigating effect of high-rise structures on surface temperatures during daylight hours. This finding challenges some common assumptions about high-rise areas being warmer. Conversely, the positive association between LST and building density and height at night emphasizes the complexity of nocturnal thermal patterns in Athens. The city's topography, including its proximity

to the coast and specific urban layouts, contributes to these distinct thermal behaviors. The LCZ analysis provided detailed insights into how different zones within Athens contribute to overall temperature patterns, guiding urban planners in understanding thermal vulnerabilities across the city. Despite the modeling's overall capability to capture spatial patterns, the systematic errors identified, especially in heavily vegetated areas, underscore the need for fine-tuning the models to Athens' specific conditions. This nuanced understanding is crucial for devising locally tailored strategies to address heat-related challenges in Athens' urban planning and development. Table 3.1 depicts the characteristics of all proposed LCZ categories and Table 3.2 presents the categorization of Athen's areas based on the LCZ matrix.

Table 3.1 The surface parameters used in the Single-layer Urban Canopy Model (SLUCM) scheme (Agathangelidis, Cartalis, & Santamouris, 2020)

Parameters ¹	LCZ 2 ₁	LCZ 2	LCZ 3	LCZ 5	LCZ 6	LCZ 8	LCZ 9	LCZ E
H (m)	20	14	9	12	9	7.5	8	7.5
H_{std} (m)	5	4.5	3.5	3.5	2.5	2	2	2
W (m)	10	11	9.5	15	15	25	20	35
R (m)	12	12	12	12	12	20	12	20
Q_F ($W\ m^{-2}$)	60	40	20	20	20	10	10	10
α_r (-)	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.15	0.2	0.15	0.2
α_w (-)	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
α_g (-)	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17
ε_r (-)	0.935	0.935	0.935	0.935	0.93	0.91	0.93	0.935
ε_w (-)	0.93	0.93	0.93	0.93	0.93	0.93	0.93	0.93
ε_g (-)	0.95	0.95	0.95	0.95	0.95	0.95	0.95	0.95
C_r ($J\ m^{-3}\ K^{-1}$)	2	2	2	2	1.4	2	1.4	2
C_w ($J\ m^{-3}\ K^{-1}$)	2	2	2	2	2	2	2.5	2
C_g ($J\ m^{-3}\ K^{-1}$)	2.1	2.1	2.1	2.1	2.1	2.1	2.1	2.1
k_r ($W\ m^{-1}\ K^{-1}$)	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1	1.5	1	1.5
k_w ($W\ m^{-1}\ K^{-1}$)	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1	1.5	2	1.5
k_g ($W\ m^{-1}\ K^{-1}$)	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4

¹ Subscripts correspond to: r : Building roof, w : Canyon wall and g : Canyon floor.

Table 3.2 The LCZ categorization of various Athen's areas and the automated weather stations used in this study for the evaluation of WRF (Agathangelidis, Cartalis, & Santamouris, 2020) along with the respective map for the broader Athens area.

Name	Code	Coordinates (E–N)	Elevation (m)	LCZ	
Alimos	AL	23°42'38"–37°55'3"	25	LCZ 2	
Ampelokipoi	AMP	23°45'30"–37°58'54"	136	LCZ 2	
Athens	ATH	23°42'55"–37°58'42"	50	LCZ 2	LCZ 2 ₁ – Compact midrise with compact highrise
Dafni-Ymittos	DIM	23°44'52"–37°56'50"	125	LCZ 2	
Faliro	FAL	23°41'34"–37°55'45"	25	LCZ 5	LCZ 2 – Compact midrise
Kifissia	KIF	23°49'12"–38°3'57"	315	LCZ 6	LCZ 3 – Compact lowrise
Maroussi	MAR	23°48'36"–38°2'54"	235	LCZ 5	LCZ 5 – Open midrise
Nikaia	NIK	23°43'10"–37°57'5"	23	LCZ 3	LCZ 6 – Open lowrise
Nea Smyrni	NS	23°38'54"–37°57'50"	51	LCZ 2	LCZ 8 – Large lowrise
Neos Kosmos	NK	23°43'57"–37°57'32"	85	LCZ 2 ₁	LCZ 9 – Sparsely built
Patissia	PAT	23°43'47"–38°1'19"	90	LCZ 2	
Penteli	PEN	23°51'52"–38°2'49"	495	LCZ 9	
Peristeri	PER	23°34'2"–37°58'2"	55	LCZ 2	
Petroupoli	PET	23°42'13"–38°0'6"	223	LCZ 5	
Psychico	PS	23°46'50"–38°1'3"	209	LCZ 6	
Vrilissia	VR	23°49'32"–38°2'17"	245	LCZ 6	

3.2. Case study LCZ areas

After a thorough analysis of Athens's built environment, the following aspects were highlighted:

- i. The majority of Athens's center is characterized by LCZ2 and LCZ2₁ typologies,
- ii. The areas with less trees and public green spaces are met in LCZ2, LCZ2₁ and LCZ3,

- iii. Some of these areas are inclined and characterized by complex terrains,
- iv. The streets' orientations are diverse; hence a common denominator was important,
- v. Trees exist on some streets, mainly citrus trees and other low vegetation,

After these first observations, further parameters were included within the searching process, namely:

a) Ability to expand or partially expand the pedestrian zone for planting purposes

An Important aspect of the areas' selection process was to target streets that offer the ability of the pedestrian's expansion in order to create surface for trees and vegetation. This parameter can only be met in very few cases in Athens, due to the narrow width of the streets and if possible, then only in the larger streets axes and not secondary streets included within potential study areas. Two solutions can be offered based the project proposal and on guidelines from the Ministry of Infrastructure and Transportation as described below:

Where possible, expand the pedestrian on one side of the street, enabling the creation of shading zones according to the proper orientation and position of the trees' zone. Of course, such a measure should be in line with the municipal Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans, as foreseen by the goals of EU's Fit for 55 agenda.

Partially expand pedestrian so as to keep parking spaces and minimize infrastructure and/or construction costs, according to the guidelines of the Ministry of Energy and Environment as depicted in Figure 3.2 (Hellenic Republic, 2022).

Figure 3.2 Proposal of street side trees planting in horizontal and vertical section (Hellenic Republic, 2022)

These two solutions were incorporated into the methodological procedure in order to choose the most suitable case study areas.

b) Potential to achieve neighbourhood upgrades through trees incorporation in the urban built environment of specific areas

Many studies have shown that implementing retrofitting actions on urban buildings or other interventions in the urban environments, leads to an overall neighborhood improvement. Retrofitting actions in the built environment, especially in the context of urban planning and redevelopment, can have positive effects on neighborhoods. Retrofitting may involve upgrading infrastructure, improving public spaces and revitalizing blighted areas. Weinsziehr et al. contend that buildings characterized by poor energy efficiency are frequently occupied by tenants or owners who hinder retrofitting efforts due to their socio-economic circumstances, concluding that households with lower net-equivalent incomes are also vulnerable to energy poverty (Weinsziehr, Grossmann, Gröger, & Bruckner, 2017). Similarly, Asamoah analyzed in his thesis that low-income neighborhoods in the DC area have faced urban challenges due to shifts in growth, leading to physical decay and increased vulnerability (Asamoah Jemimah, 2021). His research indicates that well-designed public spaces positively impact the quality of life in such areas and regenerative design can offer a methodical approach to create

restorative environments, fostering community engagement for economic and social benefits. Thus, deteriorated areas were studied so as to include social parameters into the choosing procedure.

3.3. Proposed areas per category

In the Re.Nature Cities project, numerical simulations with the ENVI-met microclimate model will be conducted for the present day and the future climatic conditions, with and without the presence of additional trees. Given that ENVI-met simulations are significantly time consuming and to achieve a reasonable compromise between simulation time and necessary scientific evidence, 2 local climate zones are finally considered for further analysis, including LCZ2 and LCZ3. Emphasis is paid on LCZs that present higher building densities and low vegetation presence as they are expected to be more susceptible to extreme events due to climate change.

3.3.1. LCZ2

Starting with category **LCZ2**, the selected area is located in Athens and more particularly surrounded by Ekatou, Theonos, Ipparchou and Deinostratou (Figure 3.2 and Figure 3.2). The area reflects typical characteristics of LCZ2 in terms of the indexes H , H_{std} and W . It covers a surface of approximately 250X180 meters and offers a flat terrain with both NS and EW orientations of its streets' axes.

Figure 3.3 and Figure 3.4 LCZ2 study area and its location in the greater city center of Athens

The following images of the streets in **LCZ2** area, clearly depict the absence of trees and vegetation as well as the building height to street width ratio

Figure 3.5 View of the Deinostratous street

Figure 3.6 View from Evdoxou and Theonos street

Figure 3.7 View from Deinostratous and Geometrou street

3.3.2. LCZ3

The study area **LCZ3** is represented by Nikaia. More specifically, the selected area is located in the south part of Nikaia, a neighborhood in the southeast of the Attica area, close to Piraeus. The area is surrounded by the streets Ikoniou, Grevenon, Kaisarias and Laodikeias. It reflects typical characteristics of LCZ3 in terms of the indexes H , H_{std} and W . It covers a surface of approximately

240X180 meters and offers a flat terrain with both NE - SW and EN - WS orientations of its streets' axes (See Figure 3.8 and Figure 3.9).

Figure 3.8 and Figure 3.9 LCZ3 study area and its location in the greater city center of Athens

The following images of the streets in **LCZ3** area, depict the low existence of trees as well as the building height to street width ratio

Figure 3.10 View of the Karaoli Dimitriou street

Figure 3.11 View of the Petrou Ralli street

Figure 3.12 View from Laodikias and Gemelou streets

The areas are summarized and coded as follows (Table 3.3).

Table 3.3 Summary of the study areas based on their LCZ categorization and main features

	LCZ2	LCZ3
Area of Athens	Athens's city centre	Nikaia
Existing vegetation	Almost none	Low
Main streets	Ekateou & Deinostratou	Kaisarias & Laodikias
Orientation of axes	N-S & E-W	NE - SW & EN - WS
Ability to expand the pedestrian zone	Yes - partially	Yes

3.4. Definition of simulation days

Due to the high temporal resolution of microclimate analysis, simulations are generally conducted on a daily basis; Re.Nature Cities project will thus focus on **typical and extreme winter and summer days** but also on a **typical spring day** so as to evaluate an intermediate period. The simulation days along with the respective climatological input boundary conditions for the microclimate simulations are derived by (Velikou, 2021). The raw datasets include high-resolution climatic data, issued by the up-to-date, dynamic regional climate model RegCM4 for a reference period (i.e. 1980-2000) and for two future periods (2041-2060 and 2081-2100). Regional climate model RegCM4 (version 4.4.5.1) is a hydrostatic, compressible, with sigma-p vertical coordinates model (Elguindi N., 2014) that was originally developed by the National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR). Its dynamical core is similar to that of the hydrostatic version of the NCAR-PSU Mesoscale Model version 5 (MM5) (Grell, Dudhia, & Stauffer, 1994). The initial spatial resolution of the model is 25x25km and the simulation is driven by the HadGEM2 general circulation model (GCM). For the future projections the model is using RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenario. The RCP4.5 scenario is an intermediate pathway with no exceedance of radiative forcing at a stabilization level of $\sim 4.5 \text{ W/m}^2$, whereas RCP8.5 is a high-end baseline scenario with very high GHG emissions and a radiative forcing of 8.5 W/m^2 at the end of the century. The main physics configurations of the model are shown in the Table 1 and are described in detail in (Velikou, Tolika, Anagnostopoulou, & Zanis, 2019)

Table 3.4: Configuration parameters of the RegCM4 model

Configuration Parameter	Selected Parameterization
Driving Field	HadGEM2
RCP (Future Scenario)	RCP4.5 / RCP8.5
Cumulus Scheme	Grell (over land)
	MIT-Emanuel (over ocean)
Convective Closure Scheme	Fritch-Chappell
Planetary Boundary Layer Scheme	UW Planetary Boundary Layer
Ocean Flux Scheme	Zeng et al.
Land Surface Model	Biosphere-Atmosphere Transfer Scheme

To generate the weather files in a finer spatial resolution, the dynamical downscaling of the RegCM4 model is performed after nesting the 25x25km simulations for the model's initial and boundary conditions. The spatial resolution of the final simulations is 10x10km and focus on Greece. The simulations cover the reference periods 1981-2000, and two future periods 2041-2060 and 2081-2100 for both RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 emission scenarios. The following map depicts the different grids generated by the RegCM4 model for the area of Greece, at a spatial resolution of 10x10km. For this previously mentioned case study areas, the following grid points have been defined.

- For the LCZ3-Nikaia: grid point 11185
- For the LCZ2-Athens central area: grid point 11186

Figure 3.18. map of Greece, indicating the different grids of the RegM4 model at a spatial resolution of 10x10km

For the purposes of this study, three meteorological parameters are utilized for three selected grid points (the closest to the examined case study areas, previously defined). The data derived from the 10x10km simulations include air temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), relative humidity (%) and wind speed (m/s). The output weather files have a 3-hour temporal resolution. Additionally, the 3-hourly mean data over each 20-year period are calculated and based on the latter output, the typical and extreme simulation days are defined. At the next step, these parameters will constitute the input boundary conditions for the ENVI-met microclimate simulations. The following figures depict the hourly air temperature and relative humidity evolution, for the typical mean day of the winter, summer and spring period for 1981-2000, 2041-2060 and 2080-2099. For the future periods, the representative days are defined both for the RCP4.5 and the RCP.8.5 emission scenarios. In terms of wind speed, the average daily values during the mean typical days, as derived by the analysis of the RegCM4 output are also given for each period.

The following diagrams depict the diurnal T_{air} and RH evolution during typical summer, winter and spring days, for both case study areas, both emission scenarios and the 3 examined periods.

For the LCZ2- Athens central area: grid point 11186
Tair and RH evolution for the typical winter, summer and spring day for the 1980-2000

Tair evolution - Mean January day -period 1980-2000

RH evolution - Mean January day -period 1980-2000

Tair evolution - Mean April day -period 1980-2000

RH evolution - Mean April day -period 1980-2000

Tair evolution - Mean July day - period 1980-2000

RH evolution - Mean July day - period 1980-2000

- mean daily wind speed/january: 7.0m/s
- mean daily wind speed/april: 6.30m/s
- mean daily wind speed/july:7.79m/s

For the LCZ2-Athens central area: grid point 11186

Tair and RH evolution for the typical winter, summer and spring day for the reference period 2040-2060 under the **RCP4.5** scenario

- mean daily wind speed/january: 7.13m/s
- mean daily wind speed/april: 6.13m/s
- mean daily wind speed/july:7.83m/s

For the LCZ2- Athens central area: grid point 11186

Tair and RH evolution for the typical winter, summer and spring day for the 2080-2099 under the **RCP4.5** scenario

- mean daily wind speed/january: 6.74m/s
- mean daily wind speed/april: 5.68m/s
- mean daily wind speed/july:7.69m/s

For the LCZ3-Nikaia: grid point 11185

Tair and RH evolution for the typical winter, summer and spring day for the reference period 1980-2000

- mean daily wind speed/january: 8.5m/s
- mean daily wind speed/april: 7.3 m/s
- mean daily wind speed/july:8.7m/s

For the LCZ3-Nikaia: grid point 11185

Tair and RH evolution for the typical winter, summer and spring day for the future period 2040-2060 under the **RCP4.5** scenario

- mean daily wind speed/january: 7.53m/s
- mean daily wind speed/april: 8.15m/s
- mean daily wind speed/july: 8.63m/s

For the LCZ3-Nikaia: grid point 11185

Tair and RH evolution for the typical winter, summer and spring day for the future period 2080-2099 under the **RCP4.5** scenario

- mean daily wind speed/january: 8.21m/s
- mean daily wind speed/april: 6.74m/s
- mean daily wind speed/july: 8.56m/s

For the LCZ2-Athens central area: grid point 11186

Tair and RH evolution for the typical winter, summer and spring day for the future period 2040-2060 under the **RCP8.5** scenario

- mean daily wind speed/january: 6.97 m/s
- mean daily wind speed/april: 6.17m/s
- mean daily wind speed/july: 7.99m/s

For the LCZ2-Athens central area: grid point 11186

Tair and RH evolution for the typical winter, summer and spring day for the future period **2080-2099** under the **RCP8.5** scenario

- mean daily wind speed/january:6.76 m/s
- mean daily wind speed/april: 6.75 m/s
- mean daily wind speed/july:7.32 m/s

For the LCZ3 Nikaia, Grid Point 11185,

Tair and RH evolution for the typical winter, summer and spring day for the future period **2040-2060** under the **RCP8.5** scenario

- mean daily wind speed/january: 8.54m/s
- mean daily wind speed/april: 7.22m/s
- mean daily wind speed/july: 8.93m/s

For the LCZ3 Nikaia, Grid Point 11185

Tair and RH evolution for the typical winter, summer and spring day for the future period 2080-2099 under the RCP8.5 scenario

- mean daily wind speed/january: 8.24m/s
- mean daily wind speed/april: 7.90m/s
- mean daily wind speed/july:8.28 m/s

Finally, in order to define the **extreme summer and winter days**, the following approach was used: The minimum and maximum temperature values, for each day of the three examined periods, were calculated from the respective 3h daily temperature values. As a second step, in order to find the days with the absolute minimum and maximum temperature, the absolute minimum value was calculated from all minimum values and the absolute maximum value was calculated from all maximum values of each examined timeseries. Thus, the following extreme days were defined.

For the LCZ2-Athens central area: grid point 11186

Tair and RH evolution for an extreme summer and winter day for the reference period 1980-2000

Hour	Extreme summer day, 06/07/1999			Extreme winter day, 30/12/1983		
	Tair	RH	Wind Speed	Tair	RH	Wind Speed
	°C	%	m/s	°C	%	m/s
0	26.99	42.53	4.02	-9.56	73.66	8.06
1	26.85	38.79	4.02	-10.07	73.08	8.06
2	26.70	35.05	4.02	-10.59	72.50	8.06
3	26.55	31.32	4.02	-11.10	71.92	8.06
4	27.71	32.73	4.02	-11.67	75.56	8.06
5	28.88	34.15	4.02	-12.24	79.21	8.06
6	30.05	35.56	4.02	-12.81	82.85	8.06
7	33.14	29.68	4.02	-11.45	78.98	8.06
8	36.23	23.80	4.02	-10.09	75.12	8.06
9	39.32	17.92	4.02	-8.73	71.26	8.06
10	38.63	19.35	4.02	-7.88	74.27	8.06
11	37.94	20.77	4.02	-7.02	77.28	8.06
12	37.25	22.19	4.02	-6.17	80.29	8.06
13	36.85	22.40	4.02	-5.58	84.68	8.06
14	36.44	22.62	4.02	-5.00	89.08	8.06
15	36.04	22.84	4.02	-4.42	93.47	8.06
16	32.45	26.35	4.02	-4.68	81.66	8.06
17	28.86	29.86	4.02	-4.95	69.84	8.06
18	25.27	33.37	4.02	-5.21	58.03	8.06
19	24.89	35.48	4.02	-5.57	68.54	8.06
20	24.52	37.58	4.02	-5.92	79.04	8.06
21	24.14	39.68	4.02	-6.28	89.55	8.06
22	26.33	36.68	4.02	-6.87	85.57	8.06
23	28.52	33.68	4.02	-7.45	81.60	8.06
24	30.70	30.68	4.02	-8.03	77.63	8.06

For the LCZ2-Athens central area: grid point 11186

*Tair and RH evolution for an extreme summer and winter day for 2040-2060-**RCP4.5** emission scenario*

*Tair and RH evolution for an extreme summer and winter day for 2040-2060-**RCP8.5** emission scenario*

Hour	Extreme summer day, 26/07/2045			Extreme winter day, 29/01/2051		
	Tair °C	RH %	Wind Speed m/s	Tair °C	RH %	Wind Speed m/s
0	29.61	28.53	6.75	-8.19	85.66	10.58
1	29.33	28.48	6.75	-8.02	82.89	10.58
2	29.06	28.44	6.75	-7.85	80.12	10.58
3	28.78	28.39	6.75	-7.67	77.34	10.58
4	30.42	28.06	6.75	-7.51	79.34	10.58
5	32.06	27.73	6.75	-7.34	81.33	10.58
6	33.71	27.40	6.75	-7.17	83.32	10.58
7	35.54	24.24	6.75	-5.81	79.41	10.58
8	37.37	21.08	6.75	-4.44	75.50	10.58
9	39.21	17.91	6.75	-3.07	71.59	10.58
10	39.70	18.16	6.75	-2.15	71.67	10.58
11	40.18	18.41	6.75	-1.22	71.75	10.58
12	40.67	18.65	6.75	-0.30	71.83	10.58
13	39.87	18.86	6.75	-0.94	76.92	10.58
14	39.07	19.07	6.75	-1.57	82.02	10.58
15	38.26	19.28	6.75	-2.21	87.12	10.58
16	36.21	20.52	6.75	-2.60	88.88	10.58
17	34.17	21.75	6.75	-3.00	90.64	10.58
18	32.12	22.98	6.75	-3.40	92.40	10.58
19	30.74	29.39	6.75	-3.39	93.16	10.58
20	29.37	35.80	6.75	-3.38	93.92	10.58
21	27.99	42.21	6.75	-3.38	94.68	10.58
22	29.93	36.70	6.75	-3.73	90.78	10.58
23	31.86	31.19	6.75	-4.08	86.89	10.58
24	33.79	25.67	6.75	-4.42	82.99	10.58

Hour	Extreme summer day, 17/08/2041			Extreme winter day, 14/01/2040		
	Tair °C	RH %	Wind Speed m/s	Tair °C	RH %	Wind Speed m/s
0	27.47	36.41	6.59	-7.66	58.35	6.30
1	27.63	35.84	6.59	-7.50	66.79	6.30
2	27.78	35.28	6.59	-7.35	75.22	6.30
3	27.94	34.72	6.59	-7.19	83.66	6.30
4	29.19	32.41	6.59	-7.03	80.73	6.30
5	30.45	30.10	6.59	-6.87	77.80	6.30
6	31.71	27.80	6.59	-6.72	74.87	6.30
7	33.90	24.85	6.59	-4.64	67.52	6.30
8	36.10	21.91	6.59	-2.56	60.16	6.30
9	38.29	18.96	6.59	-0.48	52.81	6.30
10	39.37	17.72	6.59	0.78	51.04	6.30
11	40.45	16.47	6.59	2.04	49.28	6.30
12	41.54	15.23	6.59	3.31	47.52	6.30
13	39.38	20.47	6.59	1.58	55.05	6.30
14	37.22	25.71	6.59	-0.16	62.57	6.30
15	35.07	30.95	6.59	-1.89	70.10	6.30
16	32.49	36.43	6.59	-1.90	69.18	6.30
17	29.91	41.92	6.59	-1.91	68.27	6.30
18	27.33	47.40	6.59	-1.92	67.35	6.30
19	27.00	52.52	6.59	-1.46	63.96	6.30
20	26.66	57.64	6.59	-0.99	60.57	6.30
21	26.33	62.77	6.59	-0.53	57.18	6.30
22	28.21	53.27	6.59	-1.32	59.45	6.30
23	30.08	43.78	6.59	-2.10	61.71	6.30
24	31.96	34.28	6.59	-2.88	63.98	6.30

For the LCZ2-Athens central area: grid point 11186

Tair and RH evolution for an extreme summer and winter day for 2080-2099-RCP4.5 emission scenario

Tair and RH evolution for an extreme summer and winter day for 2080-2099-RCP8.5 emission scenario

Hour	Extreme summer day, 05/07/2093			Extreme winter day, 20/01/2090		
	Tair °C	RH %	Wind Speed m/s	Tair °C	RH %	Wind Speed m/s
0	27.47	39.08	4.70	-1.59	68.25	7.71
1	27.35	38.27	4.70	-2.31	67.03	7.71
2	27.22	37.47	4.70	-3.04	65.80	7.71
3	27.10	36.66	4.70	-3.76	64.57	7.71
4	29.14	34.98	4.70	-3.87	65.21	7.71
5	31.19	33.30	4.70	-3.98	65.84	7.71
6	33.23	31.62	4.70	-4.09	66.47	7.71
7	35.47	26.88	4.70	-3.40	63.08	7.71
8	37.70	22.15	4.70	-2.70	59.69	7.71
9	39.94	17.42	4.70	-2.01	56.29	7.71
10	40.77	17.25	4.70	-1.37	53.80	7.71
11	41.60	17.09	4.70	-0.72	51.30	7.71
12	42.42	16.93	4.70	-0.08	48.81	7.71
13	41.38	17.53	4.70	-0.47	56.24	7.71
14	40.33	18.12	4.70	-0.86	63.68	7.71
15	39.29	18.72	4.70	-1.26	71.12	7.71
16	36.73	23.33	4.70	-1.01	67.55	7.71
17	34.18	27.94	4.70	-0.76	63.99	7.71
18	31.62	32.56	4.70	-0.51	60.43	7.71
19	30.50	33.65	4.70	-1.04	66.08	7.71
20	29.38	34.75	4.70	-1.56	71.74	7.71
21	28.26	35.85	4.70	-2.09	77.39	7.71
22	30.06	33.44	4.70	-2.03	72.98	7.71
23	31.86	31.02	4.70	-1.98	68.58	7.71
24	33.67	28.60	4.70	-1.92	64.17	7.71

Hour	Extreme summer day, 12/07/2080			Extreme winter day, 12/01/2090		
	Tair °C	RH %	Wind Speed m/s	Tair °C	RH %	Wind Speed m/s
0	31.82	31.45	6.93	0.18	93.34	10.88
1	31.58	29.94	6.93	-0.32	89.96	10.88
2	31.34	28.43	6.93	-0.82	86.57	10.88
3	31.11	26.92	6.93	-1.32	83.19	10.88
4	32.58	25.10	6.93	-1.54	85.91	10.88
5	34.05	23.29	6.93	-1.77	88.64	10.88
6	35.52	21.47	6.93	-1.99	91.36	10.88
7	37.40	19.71	6.93	-1.70	86.27	10.88
8	39.28	17.94	6.93	-1.41	81.18	10.88
9	41.16	16.18	6.93	-1.12	76.09	10.88
10	41.94	15.23	6.93	-0.86	74.99	10.88
11	42.72	14.29	6.93	-0.60	73.89	10.88
12	43.50	13.34	6.93	-0.34	72.80	10.88
13	42.82	14.15	6.93	-0.92	71.45	10.88
14	42.14	14.95	6.93	-1.49	70.11	10.88
15	41.46	15.75	6.93	-2.06	68.76	10.88
16	39.78	17.56	6.93	-2.24	68.89	10.88
17	38.09	19.37	6.93	-2.41	69.03	10.88
18	36.41	21.18	6.93	-2.58	69.16	10.88
19	35.34	24.98	6.93	-2.34	71.16	10.88
20	34.26	28.77	6.93	-2.10	73.15	10.88
21	33.19	32.56	6.93	-1.85	75.15	10.88
22	34.38	29.16	6.93	-1.70	76.34	10.88
23	35.58	25.76	6.93	-1.54	77.54	10.88
24	36.77	22.36	6.93	-1.39	78.73	10.88

For the LCZ3-Nikaia area: grid point 11185

Tair and RH evolution for an extreme summer and winter day for the reference period 1980-2000

Hour	Extreme summer day, 05/07/1999			Extreme winter day, 30/12/1983		
	Tair °C	RH %	Wind Speed m/s	Tair °C	RH %	Wind Speed m/s
0	22.82	61.13	5.96	-9.56	115.48	11.20
1	22.96	58.66	5.96	-10.07	117.55	11.20
2	23.11	56.20	5.96	-10.59	119.61	11.20
3	23.25	53.73	5.96	-11.10	121.67	11.20
4	25.25	54.25	5.96	-11.67	126.79	11.20
5	27.26	54.78	5.96	-12.24	131.91	11.20
6	29.27	55.30	5.96	-12.81	137.03	11.20
7	31.42	47.03	5.96	-11.45	135.40	11.20
8	33.58	38.77	5.96	-10.09	133.77	11.20
9	35.74	30.50	5.96	-8.73	132.14	11.20
10	36.86	29.57	5.96	-7.88	124.62	11.20
11	37.97	28.64	5.96	-7.02	117.11	11.20
12	39.09	27.71	5.96	-6.17	109.59	11.20
13	38.49	35.28	5.96	-5.58	107.68	11.20
14	37.89	42.85	5.96	-5.00	105.77	11.20
15	37.29	50.42	5.96	-4.42	103.86	11.20
16	34.84	45.84	5.96	-4.68	99.78	11.20
17	32.40	41.26	5.96	-4.95	95.69	11.20
18	29.95	36.67	5.96	-5.21	91.61	11.20
19	29.27	37.02	5.96	-5.57	98.87	11.20
20	28.60	37.36	5.96	-5.92	106.14	11.20
21	27.92	37.71	5.96	-6.28	113.40	11.20
22	28.83	39.86	5.96	-6.87	114.13	11.20
23	29.75	42.00	5.96	-7.45	114.87	11.20
24	30.67	44.15	5.96	-8.03	115.60	11.20

For the LCZ3-Nikaia area: grid point 11185

*Tair and RH evolution for an extreme summer and winter day for 2040-2060-**RCP4.5** emission scenario*

*Tair and RH evolution for an extreme summer and winter day for 2040-2060-**RCP8.5** emission scenario*

Hour	Extreme summer day, 24/07/2045			Extreme winter day, 16/01/2051		
	Tair °C	RH %	Wind Speed m/s	Tair °C	RH %	Wind Speed m/s
0	28.48	52.36	5.59	0.32	109.56	15.68
1	28.32	50.69	5.59	0.14	112.35	15.68
2	28.16	49.01	5.59	-0.03	115.14	15.68
3	28.00	47.34	5.59	-0.21	117.92	15.68
4	28.66	45.42	5.59	-0.44	118.76	15.68
5	29.32	43.50	5.59	-0.66	119.60	15.68
6	29.99	41.58	5.59	-0.89	120.43	15.68
7	31.23	37.88	5.59	-0.93	121.50	15.68
8	32.47	34.18	5.59	-0.98	122.57	15.68
9	33.72	30.48	5.59	-1.03	123.63	15.68
10	34.07	29.83	5.59	-0.40	117.59	15.68
11	34.42	29.19	5.59	0.22	111.54	15.68
12	34.78	28.54	5.59	0.85	105.49	15.68
13	34.99	27.85	5.59	1.13	105.33	15.68
14	35.20	27.16	5.59	1.41	105.17	15.68
15	35.41	26.48	5.59	1.69	105.01	15.68
16	35.15	26.86	5.59	1.92	102.11	15.68
17	34.89	27.25	5.59	2.16	99.21	15.68
18	34.64	27.64	5.59	2.40	96.31	15.68
19	33.91	29.73	5.59	2.05	97.98	15.68
20	33.18	31.81	5.59	1.69	99.65	15.68
21	32.45	33.90	5.59	1.34	101.32	15.68
22	32.36	34.61	5.59	1.08	104.20	15.68
23	32.27	35.32	5.59	0.82	107.08	15.68
24	32.18	36.04	5.59	0.56	109.96	15.68

Hour	Extreme summer day, 17/08/2041			Extreme winter day, 23/01/2048		
	Tair °C	RH %	Wind Speed m/s	Tair °C	RH %	Wind Speed m/s
0	28.55	47.49	7.18	2.28	105.14	14.00
1	29.01	47.01	7.18	1.89	108.19	14.00
2	29.48	46.53	7.18	1.49	111.24	14.00
3	29.94	46.05	7.18	1.10	114.29	14.00
4	29.72	47.05	7.18	1.08	115.65	14.00
5	29.49	48.04	7.18	1.06	117.01	14.00
6	29.27	49.04	7.18	1.03	118.37	14.00
7	30.56	44.69	7.18	1.34	114.23	14.00
8	31.84	40.34	7.18	1.65	110.10	14.00
9	33.13	35.99	7.18	1.96	105.96	14.00
10	33.64	33.41	7.18	2.24	105.17	14.00
11	34.15	30.83	7.18	2.52	104.38	14.00
12	34.66	28.25	7.18	2.81	103.59	14.00
13	32.18	43.02	7.18	2.91	103.73	14.00
14	29.70	57.79	7.18	3.02	103.87	14.00
15	27.22	72.56	7.18	3.13	104.01	14.00
16	27.92	65.05	7.18	3.25	104.71	14.00
17	28.63	57.54	7.18	3.37	105.42	14.00
18	29.34	50.03	7.18	3.49	106.12	14.00
19	28.87	55.78	7.18	3.63	104.28	14.00
20	28.41	61.52	7.18	3.78	102.43	14.00
21	27.95	67.27	7.18	3.92	100.58	14.00
22	28.63	61.38	7.18	3.43	102.80	14.00
23	29.32	55.48	7.18	2.95	105.03	14.00
24	30.01	49.58	7.18	2.46	107.26	14.00

For the LCZ3-Nikaia: grid point 11185

Tair and RH evolution for an extreme summer and winter day for 2080-2099-RCP4.5 emission scenario

Tair and RH evolution for an extreme summer and winter day for 2080-2099-RCP8.5 emission scenario

Hour	Extreme summer day, 03/07/2088			Extreme winter day, 20/01/2090		
	Tair °C	RH %	Wind Speed m/s	Tair °C	RH %	Wind Speed m/s
0	29.07	46.04	5.69	4.69	79.44	10.47
1	29.16	44.18	5.69	4.04	83.91	10.47
2	29.25	42.33	5.69	3.39	88.39	10.47
3	29.34	40.48	5.69	2.75	92.86	10.47
4	30.01	39.56	5.69	2.65	93.22	10.47
5	30.68	38.64	5.69	2.55	93.57	10.47
6	31.35	37.72	5.69	2.46	93.93	10.47
7	32.00	37.64	5.69	2.52	92.87	10.47
8	32.66	37.56	5.69	2.58	91.81	10.47
9	33.31	37.48	5.69	2.63	90.75	10.47
10	34.09	33.48	5.69	3.12	87.78	10.47
11	34.87	29.47	5.69	3.61	84.82	10.47
12	35.65	25.47	5.69	4.10	81.85	10.47
13	35.76	24.41	5.69	4.45	81.70	10.47
14	35.87	23.35	5.69	4.80	81.55	10.47
15	35.98	22.29	5.69	5.15	81.40	10.47
16	35.47	25.32	5.69	5.33	78.45	10.47
17	34.96	28.36	5.69	5.50	75.50	10.47
18	34.45	31.40	5.69	5.68	72.56	10.47
19	33.67	33.27	5.69	5.20	77.03	10.47
20	32.90	35.14	5.69	4.72	81.50	10.47
21	32.13	37.01	5.69	4.24	85.97	10.47
22	32.31	36.25	5.69	4.15	85.59	10.47
23	32.48	35.49	5.69	4.05	85.22	10.47
24	32.66	34.73	5.69	3.96	84.84	10.47

Hour	Extreme summer day, 21/07/2091			Extreme winter day, 12/01/2090		
	Tair °C	RH %	Wind Speed m/s	Tair °C	RH %	Wind Speed m/s
0	30.83	41.34	5.34	6.04	108.53	13.85
1	30.53	42.70	5.34	5.56	108.58	13.85
2	30.23	44.06	5.34	5.07	108.63	13.85
3	29.93	45.42	5.34	4.58	108.68	13.85
4	30.03	47.29	5.34	4.25	109.67	13.85
5	30.13	49.16	5.34	3.92	110.66	13.85
6	30.23	51.03	5.34	3.60	111.64	13.85
7	31.79	46.11	5.34	3.44	111.55	13.85
8	33.35	41.20	5.34	3.28	111.46	13.85
9	34.90	36.28	5.34	3.13	111.37	13.85
10	35.47	32.49	5.34	3.38	108.85	13.85
11	36.04	28.71	5.34	3.63	106.33	13.85
12	36.62	24.92	5.34	3.88	103.81	13.85
13	37.04	23.99	5.34	4.14	100.87	13.85
14	37.47	23.07	5.34	4.39	97.94	13.85
15	37.90	22.14	5.34	4.65	95.00	13.85
16	36.08	28.13	5.34	4.68	94.71	13.85
17	34.25	34.12	5.34	4.71	94.41	13.85
18	32.43	40.12	5.34	4.74	94.11	13.85
19	32.54	39.31	5.34	4.78	94.85	13.85
20	32.65	38.49	5.34	4.82	95.59	13.85
21	32.76	37.68	5.34	4.86	96.33	13.85
22	32.91	37.58	5.34	4.72	98.78	13.85
23	33.05	37.47	5.34	4.58	101.23	13.85
24	33.20	37.37	5.34	4.43	103.68	13.85

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